

Analysis of Uplink and Downlink Spatial Channel Reciprocity When Using Asymmetric Transceiver

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Abstract—A novel millimeter-wave massive MIMO system using asymmetric transceiver, i.e., unequal number of transmitting (Tx) and receiving (Rx) radio frequency chains, is expected to maintain the advantages of conventional fully digital beamforming architectures, but partly reduce the implementation cost and power consumption. However, uplink and downlink radio channels may become non-reciprocal due to the different dimensions of Tx-Rx antenna arrays. In this paper, we analyze the reciprocity of radio channels observed by practical antenna patterns with different beamwidths. Two metrics are leveraged to measure spatial channel reciprocity based on 142 GHz outdoor channel measurement data and 28 GHz indoor ray-tracing simulation data. The power angular spectrum (PAS) reciprocity of uplink and downlink radio channels does not hold when base station Tx array has more elements than Rx array. Meanwhile, it becomes increasingly likely that in the extreme case (e.g., significant beamwidth difference between Tx and Rx beam patterns), pronounced angle reciprocity can still be observed in the sparse channels with less multipath components.

Index Terms—Asymmetric transceiver, PAS and angle reciprocity, spatial channel reciprocity, uplink and downlink channels

I. INTRODUCTION

MILLIMETER-WAVE (mmWave) massive multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO) technology has shown promising results in enabling high-throughput communication [1], [2], and is expected to be widely deployed in real-world environments to boost up the mobile broadband services. Implementation of large-scale antenna arrays can provide sufficient beamforming gains to compensate for the severe path loss in mmWave band. In this context, hybrid beamforming (HBF) has drawn considerable attention to balance flexibility, energy efficiency, and implementation cost trade-offs, while still meeting the required transmission performance compared with analog beamforming and fully digital beamforming (DBF) [3], [4].

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A more practical HBF massive MIMO system, i.e., sub- or partially connected HBF architecture, is developed by combining multiple array elements into subarray modules, where each subarray is connected with an independent radio frequency (RF) chain and then forms a beam pointing to specific direction via phase and gain control [5]–[7]. The number of data streams is upper limited by the number of RF chains or beams [3] and each beam only benefits from the gain of the subarray. Coverage or signal outage is the main bottleneck in mmWave networks, however, such architecture cannot achieve the full array gain. In addition, HBF design becomes more challenging with increasing the number of antenna elements in terms of the HBF optimization problem and computational complexity especially when considering several practical constraints on RF components, e.g., phase shifters and variable gain amplifiers. The heavy beam training overhead for channel estimation introduced in HBF systems will cause significantly performance degradation.

Despite the current global 5G mmWave rollout adopting HBF architectures, it becomes increasingly likely that conventional DBF architectures (one dedicated RF chain per antenna element) will come true for mmWave communications once the manufacturing cost and power consumption of RF devices dramatically reduced in the near future [8]. In order to maintain the key advantages of fully DBF architecture, e.g., improved dynamic range, flexible beam management, and enhanced transmission capacity, and somewhat reduce its hardware cost, an asymmetric DBF (ABF) architecture was proposed in [2], [9]. As shown in Fig. 1, base station (BS) is equipped with fully DBF arrays, while the number of transmitting (Tx) channels for downlink transmission is much larger than that of receiving (Rx) channels for uplink reception. For an ordinal array with isotropic radiators placed at a uniform spacing of half wavelength, the array gain and effective isotropic radiated power (EIRP) are directly proportional to the number of antenna elements. Thus, increasing the number of radiating elements could produce a high-directive radiation pattern together with high-resolution beam steering. In Fig. 1, the BS downlink Tx beam is much narrower than uplink Rx beam. On the user equipment (UE) side, DBF is also employed where transceiver can be either symmetric or asymmetric.

Even though the asymmetric transceiver is employed on the BS side, the conventional DBF scheme is followed for each separate uplink or downlink. Compared with the HBF systems, ABF system inherits the advantages of DBF, which provides more beams with higher beamforming gain and supports wide-angle beam scanning for signal transmission. The

Fig. 1. The diagram of the ABF mmWave massive MIMO system using asymmetric transceiver on the BS side.

BS can get rid of complicated beam management protocols especially in high mobility scenarios, while the system is still available to maintain a sufficient power level for uplink reception [10]. Moreover, the 5G/6G wireless communication systems promise to support various emerging applications, making the uplink/downlink traffic asymmetry more and more pronounced, e.g., much higher downlink data rate and spectral efficiency than uplink [11]. Fortunately, such ABF system could optimize the resource utilization depending on the traffic demand. Compared with the symmetric DBF systems, less Rx RF chains used in ABF system leads to a reduction in hardware costs and power consumption, as well as the uplink pilot overhead for channel estimation. An ABF system operating at 3.5 GHz with 64-Tx and 16-Rx channels has been developed in [12] and the mmWave implementation is already on the way [2].

Radio channel consists of propagation channel and antennas, where the wireless system actually operates in the radio channel observed via antennas. Due to using asymmetric BS Tx and Rx beams for downlink transmission and uplink reception, respectively, we would have to raise the question of whether the radio channel reciprocity still hold. If so, it makes the proposed ABF system more competitive without increasing complexity in signal processing. In this paper, based on 142 GHz outdoor measurement and 28 GHz indoor ray-tracing simulation data, we evaluate the channel reciprocity by comparing power angular spectra (PASs) and potential beam directions of uplink and downlink radio channels, respectively.

II. UPLINK AND DOWNLINK RADIO CHANNEL (NON-)RECIPROCALITY

For traditional symmetric systems in the time division duplexing (TDD) mode of operation, reciprocity of uplink and downlink channels is an essential prerequisite for directly applying the estimated uplink channel state information (CSI) in downlink transmission [13]. For example, the uplink and downlink channel matrices of the symmetric DBF system are $\mathbf{H}_{UL} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ and $\mathbf{H}_{DL} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times N}$, respectively, where M and N denote the numbers of RF chains or antenna elements on the UE and BS sides, respectively. Then the reciprocity in the strict sense would mean $\mathbf{H}_{UL} = \mathbf{H}_{DL}^T$. In the frequency division duplexing (FDD) massive MIMO systems, despite instantaneous channel transfer functions cannot be reused directly, downlink CSI could still be inferred in virtue of the channel reciprocity regarding PASs and path directions [14].

Here, propagation channel is independent of transceivers and always reciprocal in all practical scenarios, however, radio channel observed by asymmetric TX/Rx analog hardware and antenna arrays may become non-reciprocal.

For the ABF system shown in Fig. 1, the assumption of uplink and downlink channel reciprocity cannot be adopted due to using asymmetric transceiver architecture. Thus, the question arises how link equivalence (especially the spatial channel information) can be profitably exploited to reconstruct downlink CSI with the aid of estimated uplink CSI. Here, we can define reciprocity based on the similarity of power angular distribution observable on, e.g., the BS side. For example, if the power observable through the BS RX array and RF chains P_{UL} approximates to the power observable by the BS TX array and RF chains P_{DL} in angle of ϕ , i.e., $P_{UL}(\phi) \approx P_{DL}(\phi)$, the uplink and downlink channels are roughly reciprocal. In [15], we proposed two multi-band spatial channel similarity measures by comparing normalized PASs and beam directions, respectively, which could be further extended to characterize PAS and angle reciprocity. For example, uplink and downlink radio channels can be formed by filtering the same propagation channel with Tx and Rx beam patterns of different half-power beamwidths (HPBW). The higher the similarity level of two beamformed channels, the more pronounced reciprocity between uplink and downlink channels. The channel reciprocity is expected to be related to the beamwidth difference between Tx and Rx beams, as well as the channel conditions, e.g., rich-scattering and sparse channels.

III. CHANNEL DATA COLLECTION AND POST-PROCESSING

A. Outdoor Channel Measurement Campaign

The 142 GHz channel data measured by Aalto university in a city center available in [16] is used for the characterization of channel non-reciprocity. A total of 12 line-of-sight (LOS) and 23 non-LOS (NLOS) links were selected with the maximum transmitter-receiver (T-R) separation distance up to 178 m. An omni-directional bicone antenna with 45° elevation HPBW was used at the Tx side, and at the Rx side, horn antenna with 10° azimuth HPBW and 40° elevation HPBW was rotated in the azimuth plane while its main lobe was fixed at the horizontal plane. The Tx and Rx antennas were both fixed at the height of 2m above the ground. Using a measurement-based ray-launcher, double-directional channel data can be estimated based on measured single-directional data. More details of the channel measurement campaign and ray-launcher can be found in [17].

B. Indoor Point Cloud Ray-Tracing Simulation

The 28 GHz indoor channel data is obtained via point cloud ray-tracing simulation in Helsinki-Vantaa airport terminal hall [18]. The point cloud used in ray-tracing simulation is refined by removing the ceiling and floor of the airport terminal, as well as human blockers. Two transmitter locations were selected in a side corridor and behind the stairs, respectively. Two kinds of Rx regions were selected resulting in a total of 1473 T1-R1 links and 1402 T2-R2 links, respectively. Note that only NLOS receiver locations were considered, which

were approximately uniformly distributed in the corresponding coverage areas. The T-R link distances range from 5 m to 70 m. The output of ray-tracing simulator includes the power, delay, and angular information for each path. Note that only 25 strongest paths for each T-R location pair are recorded in the data sheet. More details about ray-tracing configurations can be found in [19].

C. Data Post-Processing

Both channel measurement and ray-tracing simulation data shares the same data structure, where the l -th propagation path is characterized by a set of channel parameters $\{p_l, \tau_l, \phi_l, \theta_l\}$, including its received power p_l , propagation delay τ_l , azimuth angle of arrival (AOA) ϕ_l , and zenith angle of arrival (ZOA) θ_l . As the asymmetric transceiver architecture is only employed at the Rx side, the power delay angular profile (PDAP) $P(\tau, \phi, \theta)$ with respect to the direction of arrival can be written as

$$P(\tau, \phi, \theta) = \sum_{l=1}^L p_l \delta(\tau - \tau_l) \cdot \delta(\phi - \phi_l) \cdot \delta(\theta - \theta_l), \quad (1)$$

where L is the total number of multipath components (MPCs). If only azimuth beamforming is conducted, PAS with respect to azimuth plane can be synthesized as

$$P(\phi) = \sum_{\tau} \sum_{\theta} P(\tau, \phi, \theta). \quad (2)$$

Note that the antenna effect has been deembedded for both data sets and the $P(\phi)$ only characterizes the spatial power distribution of propagation channel.

The beamforming impact on the characterization of radio channels can be expressed as filtering the PAS with antenna beam pattern $G(\phi)$ as follows:

$$\hat{P}(\phi) = \int P(\varphi) G(\phi - \varphi) d\varphi. \quad (3)$$

This corresponds to steering the beam pattern to a direction ϕ and collecting the sum power from all observable MPCs weighted with the corresponding beam gains. The $\hat{P}(\phi)$ represents the PAS of radio channel, so-called as beamformed PAS. Here beam patterns of uniform linear arrays (ULAs) with different numbers of elements N are used. The normalized array factor of ULA with isotropic radiators can be written as

$$G(\phi, \phi_0) = \frac{\sin\left(\frac{N\pi d}{\lambda} [\sin \phi - \sin \phi_0]\right)}{N \sin\left(\frac{\pi d}{\lambda} [\sin \phi - \sin \phi_0]\right)}, \quad (4)$$

where λ is the wavelength, d is the inter-element spacing, and ϕ_0 is the steering angle off boresight. From (4), we can deduce that the beamwidth widens as the beam is scanned away from the boresight. To simplify the analysis, we assume that the beam pattern will not change with beam pointing angle in (3), i.e., using the beam pattern at $\phi_0 = 0^\circ$. Moreover, the beam patterns of ULAs are defined for $\phi \in [-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$ boresight half plane with all-zero phasing, while the back half plane $\phi \in [-180^\circ, -90^\circ] \cup [90^\circ, 180^\circ]$ is set to a constant -60 dB gain.

In this paper, we only consider the ABF architecture employed on the BS side while keeping the symmetric architecture on the UE side. Here, N_{Tx} and N_{Rx} denote the numbers

Fig. 2. Beam patterns of ULAs with 4, 8, 16, and 32 elements.

of antenna elements used for BS downlink transmission and uplink reception, respectively. For symmetric systems, N_{Rx} is equal to N_{Tx} , while $N_{\text{Rx}} < N_{\text{Tx}}$ for asymmetric systems. We set N_{Rx} as 4 or 8, which is a typical number of elements in azimuth for commercial phased sub-array based mmWave multibeam systems. The N_{Tx} is set as 8, 16, or 32 for the comparison of beamwidth impact on channel reciprocity. Fig. 2 depicts the beam patterns of half-wavelength-spaced ULAs with different numbers of elements.

IV. ANALYSIS, RESULTS, AND DISCUSSION

A. Reciprocity of Beamformed PASs

When we would like to reconstruct channel matrix for downlink transmission, the estimated uplink channel information can be directly reused and expanded only if both links exhibit pronounced reciprocity of beamformed PASs. The PAS similarity percentage (PSP) metric developed in [19] calculates the total variation distance between the normalized beamformed PASs as

$$\rho [\%] = 1 - \frac{\int |\bar{P}_{\text{DL}}(\phi) - \bar{P}_{\text{UL}}(\phi)| d\phi}{2}, \quad (5)$$

where $\bar{P}_{\text{DL}}(\phi)$ (or $\bar{P}_{\text{UL}}(\phi)$) denotes the normalized beamformed PAS of downlink (or uplink) channel. The larger PSP value, the more obvious uplink and downlink radio channel reciprocity with respect to beamformed PASs.

For each T-R link, we can obtain a dedicated ρ value for further statistical analysis. Fig. 3 shows the cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) of PSP index based on channel sounding data and ray-tracing simulation data, respectively. Their corresponding statistics are summarized in Table. I. The PSP is equal to 100% when the identical Tx and Rx ULAs are employed on the assumption of plane-wave incidence. The PSP value seems inversely proportional to the beamwidth ratio of Rx and Tx arrays, where high PSP value corresponds to more obvious uplink and downlink channel reciprocity. For example, in 50% of cases the PSP values exceed almost 70% for both outdoor and indoor environments with $(N_{\text{Tx}}, N_{\text{Rx}}) = (8, 4)$ or $(16, 8)$, i.e., the HPBW of Rx beam $\phi_{3\text{dB}, \text{Rx}}$ is around twice wider than $\phi_{3\text{dB}, \text{Tx}}$. Both measured and simulated results show a similar trend that the PSP values decrease with the increase of $\phi_{3\text{dB}, \text{Rx}}/\phi_{3\text{dB}, \text{Tx}}$. Moreover, the PSP values for LOS links are slightly larger than the results for NLOS links with regard to the measurement case, whereas their differences are statistically insignificant.

TABLE I
THE STATISTICS OF PSP AND POWER RATIOS R FOR MEASURED AND SIMULATION CASES USING DIFFERENT ULA CONFIGURATIONS.

(N_{TX}, N_{RX})		(8, 4)		(16, 4)		(32, 4)		(16, 8)		(32, 8)	
$\phi_{3dB,RX}/\phi_{3dB,TX}$		2.05		4.16		8.73		2.03		4.27	
Data source ^a		Meas.	Sim.	Meas.	Sim.	Meas.	Sim.	Meas.	Sim.	Meas.	Sim.
PSP [%]	10%	68.7 / 69.5	67.5	45.5 / 45.7	43.8	29.8 / 28.6	28.3	69.1 / 68.5	67.6	45.8 / 45.2	44.2
	50%	70.9 / 71.7	68.4	48.0 / 50.5	45.5	32.9 / 34.9	30.3	70.5 / 71.0	68.5	47.8 / 48.9	45.7
	90%	80.9 / 76.2	77.6	58.0 / 59.2	58.3	40.2 / 38.9	42.5	73.5 / 75.2	76.3	53.3 / 56.0	56.8
$-R$ [dB]	10%	2.54 / 1.01	1.19	4.64 / 2.66	3.11	15.76 / 4.57	6.34	2.01 / 0.70	0.81	2.74 / 1.91	2.42
	50%	0.44 / 0.03	0	0.97 / 0.23	0	2.43 / 1.11	0	0.09 / 0.01	0	0.40 / 0	0
	90%	0.01 / 0	0	0.03 / 0	0	0.12 / 0	0	0 / 0	0	0 / 0	0

^a For the measurement case, the values in the left and right sides of “/.” are extracted in LOS and NLOS scenarios, respectively. For the ray-tracing simulation case, only the results in NLOS scenario are considered.

Fig. 3. CDFs of PSP for (a) outdoor measurement case and (b) indoor ray-tracing simulation case.

B. Reciprocity of Beam Pointing Angles

With the purpose of discovering strongest directional links for downlink transmission and uplink reception, beam training protocols offer an alternative solution without explicit channel estimation. Using different Tx/Rx beams potentially results in different beam pointing angles due to different angular resolutions (i.e., HPBWs). In [19], we developed a beam direction-based channel similarity metric, which first estimates the potential beam directions based on the local maximum values of beamformed PASs $\hat{P}_{DL}(\phi)$ and $\hat{P}_{UL}(\phi)$ [20], and then calculates the power ratio of power summation over different steering angle sets observed by non-reciprocal beam patterns as

$$R \text{ [dB]} = \frac{\sum_{\phi \in \mathcal{A}_{UL}} \hat{P}_{DL}(\phi)}{\sum_{\phi \in \mathcal{A}_{DL}} \hat{P}_{DL}(\phi)}, \quad (6)$$

Fig. 4. CDFs of power ratio for outdoor measurement case (without markers) and indoor ray-tracing simulation case (with markers).

where \mathcal{A}_{DL} and \mathcal{A}_{UL} denote the azimuth angle sets of potential beam directions estimated from downlink and uplink radio channels, respectively. The power ratio R is less than or equal to 0 dB, because beamformed PAS with wider beam pattern potentially results in less number of beam directions. The $-R$ represents the power loss introduced by using different Tx and Rx beams. Larger power loss indicates that the angle reciprocity level of uplink and downlink channels will be significantly reduced.

Fig. 4 depicts the CDFs of power ratio for measured and simulated cases. The similar trend can be observed that power ratio R reduces with increase of array size gap. The power loss values for measured case are slightly larger than the simulated results due to more detectable beam directions in outdoor environments. However, in 50% of cases the R values extracted from measurement and simulation data are close to 0 dB with an exception of $(N_{TX}, N_{RX}) = (32, 4)$, which is the extreme case with about 23.2° HPBW difference between small- and large-scale antenna arrays. Thus, angle reciprocity of uplink and downlink radio channel still hold with a focus on beam directions.

In order to analyze the impact of channel condition (e.g., rich scattering or sparse channel) on uplink and downlink channel reciprocity in ABF-based system, we compare the average numbers of estimated beam directions across different

Fig. 5. Comparison of the average number of estimated beam directions across the beamformed channels filtering with different beam patterns.

scenarios as depicted in Fig. 5. The PASs of radio channels are observed by different sizes of ULAs, e.g., $N = 4, 8, 16$, and 32. We can thus derive following conclusions:

- 1) From Table I, both measured and simulated cases in general show low power loss even when beamwidth difference of Tx and Rx arrays becoming more pronounced. On the contrary to the PAS reciprocity, angle reciprocity of uplink and downlink radio channels still holds in the scenarios with less detectable beam directions.
- 2) The statistics of power loss $-R$ in different scenarios are related to the average numbers of potential beam directions. For example, more beam directions can be detected for measured LOS links compared with other links. This results in higher power loss, i.e., the reduction of the angle reciprocity, indication that estimated uplink beam direction information cannot be directly reused for downlink transmission.
- 3) The number of observed beam directions is proportional to the antenna array size. In other words, the increased number of ULA elements leads to narrower beam pattern (see green line in Fig. 5) and higher angular resolution, which enables to detect more beam directions. Increasing beam number difference between non-reciprocal uplink and downlink radio channels generally results in lower power ratio.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we analyze the spatial channel reciprocity in massive MIMO systems when using asymmetric Tx and Rx arrays for downlink transmission and uplink reception, respectively. The PSP and beam direction based metrics are respectively utilized for measuring PAS and angle reciprocity based on 142 GHz outdoor channel sounding data and 28 GHz indoor ray-tracing simulation data. The reciprocity of beamformed PASs only holds when the size of the BS Tx antenna array is not significantly (e.g., no more than twice) larger than the Rx antenna array. The angle reciprocity is determined not only by the beamwidth difference between the Tx and Rx arrays, but also by the propagation channel. For the scenario having more scatterers, angle reciprocity becomes more sensitive to the Tx-Rx beamwidth difference. Furthermore, as the Tx and Rx RF front-ends differ, the

reciprocity of the uplink and downlink channel need to be evaluated considering the impact of asymmetric transceiver circuitries and antenna arrays.

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